

Prevention through Design: Clients' Pre-Construction Health and Safety Arrangements

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Abstract. Proactive management of health and safety risk often minimises ill-health, injuries and fatalities on projects. Hence, in some jurisdictions like the UK, statutory duties are placed on project Clients to make suitable arrangements for projects to be carried out without risk to health and safety. This study surveys Clients and practitioners in the UK construction industry in focus group workshops to establish seven dominant practices being employed by Clients in response to this obligation under the health and safety Regulations.

Keywords: Design for occupational health and safety. Pre-construction . Project clients . Health and safety arrangement practices . Construction

1 Introduction

The nexus between procurement and design decisions upstream of the construction supply chain and occupational safety and health (OSH) risks downstream of same has been articulated in literature and practice for many decades. This connection was informed by the lack of proactiveness on the part of parties of the construction supply chain, particularly parties upstream of the chain, in managing construction risk and the resultant poor performance of OSH risk management on construction projects [1, 2, 3, 4, 5]. There is therefore a call by scholars and practitioners for project stakeholders to accept responsibility, collectively, to minimise OSH risks on construction projects with the view that such an obligation must start from the commencement of the construction product development process [2, 4, 6, 7]. This understanding underpins the Prevention through Design (PtD) philosophy [1, 2].

The PtD philosophy informed the European Council's response to the OSH challenges of the construction industry with the adoption of Council Directive 1992/57/EEC on the implementation of minimum safety and health requirements at temporary or mobile construction sites. In 1994, the UK which was then a full member of the EU, transposed the Directive into UK legislation as part of the Construction (Design and Management) Regulations 1994 (CDM 1994). These Regulations have since been revised twice with

the current version being CDM 2015. The Regulations impose statutory health and safety duties on the traditional members of construction project stakeholders (clients, designers and contractors) to ensure that the design and production of construction products are carried out without risks to health and safety. Clients as initiators and purchasers of construction products have dominant positions on projects to influence OSH risks on projects [8, 9]. Hence, the CDM 2015 Regulations require clients to make necessary health and safety arrangements to ensure projects are inherently safe. However, the Regulations are not clear as to what specific practices should be embarked on by clients in compliance with this requirement. Thus, this study focuses on the pre-construction phase of the project development process to explore the range of practices in place, in the UK construction industry, regarding clients' health and safety arrangements as required by the Regulations.

2 Method

The study employed a qualitative research approach in undertaking this probe. A qualitative research approach is considered suitable for studying a phenomenon, including obtaining data in the form of verbal conversation from a relatively smaller number of individuals so as to capture their views on a situation [10].

Specifically, data was obtained through fourteen focus group discussions (FGDs) over a period of six weeks with over seventy practitioners in the UK construction industry with backgrounds as clients, designers, contractors as well as health and safety professionals. A FGD approach was employed, because the study's aim was to: understand and not infer; determine the range of views and not generalize; and offer insights into how the research participants recognise health and safety arrangement practices by clients – particularly at the pre-construction phase – in response to regulatory requirements [11].

The participants for the focus group workshops were purposively selected from the UK construction industry. This offered the researchers opportunity to obtain participants who were *information-rich* and could offer relevant information regarding the phenomenon being investigated [10, 12]. This study formed part of a larger investigation on how, generally, the UK construction industry complies with construction health and safety regulations and thus had partnership with professional bodies and industry partners. As a result, to recruit participants for the FGD workshops, leadership of the professional bodies and industry partners were contacted to publicise the FGD workshops within their networks. Interested participants were subsequently written to and subsequently made to complete a consent form to join the FGD workshops. Each FGD workshop was recorded to capture a vivid discussion of the session.

The data analysis process involved: (a) transcription of the FGD recordings, (b) critical reading of the transcripts to gain insights of main patterns embedded in the data, (c) loading of FGD transcripts into Nvivo version 12 software programme, (d) generation of codes and categories based on the study aim by means of an inductive coding strategy

Table 1. Categories of Clients' health and safety arrangement practices in compliance with CDM 2015

Categories	Sub-categories
Dependence on third party health and safety arrangements such as Principal Designers, CDM advisors, and health and safety consultants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Appointment of CDM advisors to perform Client roles (19) • Use of Principal Designers (PDs) (16) • Use of health and safety consultants (3)
Reliance on in-house health and safety teams and systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Design management plan or CDM management plan (13) • Setting up of in-house health and safety team (7) • Development of health and safety policy (2) • Development of loop system to utilise design health and safety feedback • Award scheme for best health and safety practice or innovation
Early project collaboration meetings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Client CDM introduction meeting among project participants prior to commencement of design (5) • Client pre-construction rehearsal and constructability review meeting before construction phase
Health and safety agenda setting through client brief	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • CDM strategy brief (3) • Client brief (2)
Reliance on project managers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Project manager coordinating design review meetings on behalf of Client (2) • Project manager listed as Client and assuming Client health and safety duties
Use of contractual arrangements between project participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Health and Safety duty requirements in terms of appointment of project parties • Client inclusion of site visits terms in appointment contracts of contractors
Use of in-house health and safety teams and structures with support from external health and safety consultants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Client internal team carries out Principal Designer role with support from health and safety advisors • Project development and design managers in charge of health and safety with external advisory support

Note: Figures in parentheses denote the number of references to such practices by the FGD workshop participants.

3.1 Dependence on Third Party Health and Safety Arrangements such as Principal Designers, CDM Advisors, and Health and Safety Consultants

Under this practice, Clients often engage the services of other entities (PDs, CDM advisors, and health and safety advisors) competent in the management of OSH on construction projects to assist them to fulfill their health and safety duties under Regulations. PDs are required by the Regulations, particularly for projects involving more than one contractor on site, to be appointed by the Client to coordinate project health and safety matters at the pre-construction phase of the project development process. On the other hand, CDM advisors as well as health and safety consultants have no such statutory roles under the Regulations. As part of Clients duty to make suitable arrangements for the management of projects without risk to health and safety, Clients often fall on these third party entities to among other things, advise Clients or make them aware of their duties under the Regulations; take active roles in the preparation of relevant pre-construction information and their subsequent dissemination to relevant project parties for optimal OSH decisions along the project supply chain; and advising clients on the appointments of project parties with relevant health and safety skills, knowledge and experience or organisational capability. As shown in Table 1, this practice appears to be most common approach in the industry with the most references

by the FGD workshops participants. 19 and 16 references for the appointment of CDM advisors to perform Client roles and use of Principal Designers, respectively.

Fig. 2. Project map of Clients' pre-construction health and safety arrangements categories

3.2 Reliance on In-House Health and Safety Teams and Systems

Informed project Clients often have well established in-house health and safety teams and systems for ensuring that the Client's duty of making suitable arrangements for projects is complied with under Regulations. Such a practice, as indicated in Table 1 includes a number of approaches. First, Clients develop design management plans or CDM management plans as part of measures to comply with their duties under the Regulations. The design or CDM management plans basically considers what the Client and other dutyholders duties are and what the Client needs to do to ensure all dutyholders are fulfilling their duties under the Regulations. A checklist is made of them as a control document during the management of health and safety matters at the pre-construction phase of the project development process. This, in addition to the appointment of CDM advisors and use of PDs, seems to be a popular practice with a reference of 13 by the workshops participants. Second, Clients set up core in-house health and safety teams to support the preparation of pre-construction information and coordinate all health and safety processes at the pre-construction phase of the project development process. This practice is often common with large infrastructure firms which have such departments embedded in their corporate structures. Third, health and safety policies and CDM manuals are developed and enforced among project parties by Clients as ways of making appropriate health and safety arrangements for projects. Fourth, some project Clients have feedback and loop systems to capture learning and lessons on prior designs and construction to benefit current and future project designs and implementation. Further, as a way of encouraging the right behaviours and decisions in respect of OSH among project parties, particularly at the pre-construction stage, some Clients have instituted internal and innovation award schemes. These last two practices (loop or feedback system and OSH award schemes) appear not to be common in the industry and are still at the embryonic stage.

3.3 Early Project Collaboration Meetings

In compliance with the Regulations to make suitable arrangements so projects can be carried out without risk to health and safety, some Clients act proactively and organize two meetings at the pre-construction phase to orient parties along the project supply chain in respect of OSH. These meetings include Client CDM introduction meeting among project participants prior to commencement of design and Client pre-construction rehearsal and constructability review meeting immediately before the construction phase.

3.4 Health and Safety Agenda Setting Through Client Brief

As indicated in Table 1, this practice comes in two forms. Use of Client brief and CDM strategy brief as part of the tools for ensuring suitable health and safety arrangements on construction projects by Clients. The Client brief is the expression of the Client requirements regarding the development of the construction project and often in there, Clients indicate their aspirations and commitments regarding health and safety management to provide direction from the outset of the project development process. This document generally is from the Client to the lead designer. However, to provide further details of project OSH risks and to ensure somewhat inclusiveness among project parties upstream of the supply chain, currently a CDM strategy brief has been introduced. This document often receives inputs from the Client, the lead designer, the PD, and any other project party appointed. In addition to the general Client requirements and how the project will be managed, this document also identifies and indicates key project hazards and OSH risks to support the optimal health and safety decisions of parties along the project supply chain.

3.5 Reliance on Project Managers

Another variant of practice regarding Clients health and safety arrangements for projects is Clients' dependence on project managers. This practice manifests in two forms as Clients relying on project managers to convene and coordinate design review meetings as well as Clients listing project managers as Clients and letting them assume Clients health and safety duties on projects. Under this practice, Clients assume that project managers have requisite health and safety skills, knowledge and experience or organisational capability, which is often not the case. This can undermine project OSH risk management performance.

3.6 Use of Contractual Arrangements between Project Participants

Clients employ contractual measures, as part of suitable project health and safety arrangements, to have project parties comply with Regulations for optimal OSH risk management performance on projects. Hence, specific health and safety requirement terms are included in the contracts of appointments of project parties. This gives power to the Client to effectively control activities of project parties, particularly from a health and safety perspective.

3.7 Use of In-house Health and Safety Teams and Structures with Support from External Health and Safety Consultants.

Depending on the capability of some Clients, there is often the practice of blending both internal and external competence regarding Clients' suitable health and safety arrangements on projects. This normally takes the form of Client internal team carrying out Principal Designer role with support from health and safety advisors as well as in-house project development and design managers being in charge of health and safety with external advisory support.

4 Conclusions

The role of Clients in ensuring optimal OSH risk management performance on projects cannot be discounted. Hence Regulations place Clients at the centre of affairs regarding the management of health and safety by requiring them to make suitable arrangements for projects such that work can be carried out without risk to health and safety. The practices Clients adopt to comply with this duty, as required by the Regulations, are not clear in construction health and safety management literature. This study has sought to empirically unearthed seven main practices by which Clients make arrangements for project health and safety with the dominant one being dependence on third party health and safety arrangements such as PDs, CDM advisors, and health and safety consultants. The identified range of practices serves as a guide for most clients who are faced with uncertainty as to how to comply with the Regulations from the perspective of pre-construction health and safety arrangements.

Acknowledgments

This research has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 837721.

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